

DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE YEARS OF
INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract: This article provides very necessary and useful information about the development of culture and art in our country, the establishment of modern culture and art institutions based on world-class best practices.

Key words: music, literature, theater, art, advertising

Today, the number of cultural and educational facilities in our country is increasing year by year, and the number of people who are willing to serve our people in these facilities, i.e. cultural workers, is also increasing. During the years of independence, our state gave priority to the development of culture and art in our country, the establishment of modern culture and art institutions based on world-class best practices, the strengthening of their material and technical base, and the comprehensive support of creative intellectuals. is coming This is especially evident in the fields of theater art, national music, architecture, and literature. In 1991, in Fergana, in 1993, in Khiva, State Puppet Theaters began to work. In 1994, puppet groups were opened under the theaters of Kashkadarya and Namangan regions. The “Turkiston” Palace, which opened in Tashkent in August 1993, has become not only a bright example of architecture, but also a venue for performances by stage groups and famous artists. 41 professional theaters operate in the republic. On March 26, 1998, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov “On the development of the

theater art of Uzbekistan” was announced. In accordance with this decree, it is necessary to study, enrich and promote the centuries-old traditions of the performing arts of Uzbekistan, to develop the theater art in all aspects, to further strengthen its material and technical base, to strengthen the spiritual “Uzbekteatr” creative-production association was established in order to ensure the active participation of theater personalities in the implementation of educational reforms. “Uzbeknavo” touring concert association was established in order to develop dance art in Uzbekistan. Issues of state support for the development of the art of music and dance were envisaged in it. Independence marked a new stage in the development of Uzbek fiction and literary studies.

The work of nationalist writers and enlighteners such as Cholpon, Otajon Hashim, Vadud Mahmud, Munavvarqori, Fitrat, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, whose works are harmful and unfairly evaluated as nationalists, began to be objectively studied. Their works were published and appeared on stage. The true nature of the Jadidism movement, its place in literary, cultural, and political life has begun to be revealed. The lives and works of great poets and thinkers such as Ahmed Yassavi, Bakirghani, Imam Ghazalli, Hoja Ahror, Bahauddin Naqshband, Husayn Boykara, Feruz, who were once unfairly condemned as representatives of religious and court literature, were studied and their works were returned to the people. Alisher Navoi's works such as “Munojot”, “Arbain”, “Tarihi anbiyo va hukamo” (“About Prophets and Governors”), which illuminate high human ideas based on religious sources, were published. In honor of independence, the holy Quran and hadiths were published. The book “Qur’an and Uzbek literature” by Hamidulla Karomatov, a talented scientist, was published. Famous scientist B. Ahmedov's “Amir Temur”, T. Malik’s “Shaitanat” novels, E. Vahidov, O. Matjon, O. Hojiyeva, H. Sultanov, A. Suyun, Y. Eshbek, H. Dostmuhammad, Sh. Uzbek national independence literature was formed thanks to the artistically perfect, ideologically mature works of poets and writers like Salimova. Buildings combining eastern and western architecture are rising in the capital and regional centers of our country, adding beauty to our cities. The National Bank, hotel

buildings, markets, bridges and roads, sports palaces and cultural the creation of recreational parks is a clear example of this. In sculpture, applied decorative arts, visual arts, dance, and film arts, mature works have been created and are being created by combining traditional and modern methods. So, in the years of independence, great achievements were made in the field of science and culture under the leadership of our government in a short period of time. As a result of the independence of Uzbekistan, the art of music, which is an important aspect of spiritual culture, began to develop very much, because the Uzbek people, who are naturally delicate, artistic and demanding of artists, music is a reflection of a wide range of spirituality. During the time of the Soviets, this type of art, which mainly became the hand of ideological domination, entered the path of freedom. The members of the society began to enjoy the art of national singing. The government of Uzbekistan, taking into account the social need of our people for national singing, has always encouraged the interest in creating musical works in the national spirit, close to the hearts of the people. Since the first days of independence, a number of music competitions have been held. In particular, in March 1992, the republican audition of tanbur, sato, koshnai, trumpet and other national music performers called "Equals of the Ages" was held in Tashkent, and in April, the audition of amateur puppet theater teams in Tashkent region. - competition, as well as auditions called "Eternal Voices" of performers of the works of famous artists Jorakhan Sultanov, Saidjon Kalonov, Komiljon Jabbarov, Nabijon Hasanov, Komiljon Otaniyozov, Fakhriddin Sadikov, Janak Shomuratov were held. At the same time, in May 1992 in the Khorezm region, folklore teams, askiya, amateurs and clowns, the 9th traditional and lapar, yalla performances held in June in Kokan, and the 11th national traditional competition held in Tashkent in August. made a great contribution to the development of our art.

The government of our country has paid attention to the effective use of the art of singing in strengthening the spiritual foundations of independence. For this purpose, in December 1995, a competition of songs on the theme "Uzbekistan-My Motherland" was announced. This competition was held in all regions, cities and districts in the spirit

of great enthusiasm, and as a result, hundreds of new songs of the independence period were created, and many talented artists appeared. More than a thousand artists participated in the first stage of the song contest "Uzbekistan - My Country" held in March 1996, more than 10 thousand new musical works were created. It should be noted that this competition was an important step in the realization of independence, Motherland, identity. The interest of our people in such an event has increased. Taking into account all this, in August 1996, a special decree was adopted "On the Song Festival of Uzbekistan - My Country".

In the decree, the third Sunday of August every year was designated as the song holiday "Uzbekistan - My Country" in order to create a wide opportunity for the creation of musical works and songs of a high artistic level that cultivate the feeling of the sacred Motherland in the hearts of citizens. At the same time, taking into account the great interest of our people in the art of singing, the tour-concert association "Uzbeknavo" was established in the presence of the Ministry of Cultural Affairs. On March 11, 1997, the decision of the government of the Republic on holding the International Music Festival "Sharq Taronalari" served as a program for the wide promotion and development of unique examples of musical art. It has become a tradition to hold the "Sharq Taronalari" International Festival in Samarkand every two years. Wide promotion of unique examples of Uzbek national art, preservation and development, development of feelings of respect and attention to our national classic art in the hearts of the young generation, it is a bond between different peoples. has been expanding the scope of cultural-spiritual relations, strengthening cultural ties, creative cooperation, and international relations.

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